

A. QUESTIONS FOR THE PHD FELLOWS

Opening Questions:

1. Both: When did you start and when did you complete your PhD? Have you done your PhD with funding (e.g., a personal fellowship or project funding)? If yes, which PhD programme funded your PhD? If MSCA, which project?
2. Both: How did you find your PhD position? Do you know the EURAXESS tool where all open EU funded PhD positions are advertised? Did you find your PhD position through EURAXESS or through other means? In the latter case, what means did you use?
3. Both: Did you find several opportunities of funding for your PhD? What motivated you to apply and select your PhD programme? (e.g., transparency of the recruitment process, resources/budget, acceptance rate, working conditions, content of research, networking possibilities, the importance given to interdisciplinary, international and intersectoral opportunities in EU funding schemes).

Mobility (Intersectoral/International/Interdisciplinary):

4. Both: Were you recruited by an academic or non-academic entity? Have you experienced any type of intersectoral and international mobility for your PhD yourself? Which one?
- 5.1. Both: If answer to question 4 is YES: How much do you think your mobility experiences have contributed to your career development, training, employability, and career opportunities?
- 5.2. Conditional for non-MSCA, if answer to question 4 is NO: How did the absence of mobility affect your career development, training, employability, and career opportunities?
6. Non-MSCA: How did your PhD programme support international and intersectoral mobility? If not, what alternatives did they offer?

Training (Supervision/Working Environment):

7. Both: What were the working conditions and employment status that you had during your PhD (e.g., fellowship vs employment contract, social security and pension contributions, full-time vs part-time)?
8. Both: In terms of support (training, resources, salary), were they sufficient to cover your living costs and research and training needs?
9. Both: How did your PhD experience help you develop technical and soft skills (e.g., critical thinking, problem-solving, analytical skills, project management, communication etc.), and which were the most beneficial for your career so far and could be transferrable to different contexts?
10. Both: How were the supervisory arrangements (co-supervision, frequency of feedback, availability, involvement of post-docs) in your program, and how did they impact your career development? How could they be further improved?

Structuring Effects:

11. Both: Have you seen an evolution in the organisation/delivery of the PhD training (shared trainings, availability/share of resources, increase of administrative or scientific support, change in the supervision) while you were pursuing your PhD?

Career Perspectives:

12. Both: How long did it take you to find your first job? What job are you currently doing? Is it different from your first job?

13. MSCA: How do you perceive the impact of participating in an MSCA project on your career perspectives compared to if you had pursued a national PhD?

14. Both: Did you collaborate with other researchers or institutions during your PhD? If so, how did these collaborations and networking opportunities enhance your research and career?

Closing Question:

15. Both: Which successful approaches or best practices from your PhD programme should be implemented in other PhD programmes to improve their effectiveness and attractiveness?

16. MSCA: could you please explain us what was the added value of your MSCA ITN PhD and what aspects should be improved?

B. QUESTIONS FOR THE SUPERVISORS

Opening Questions:

1. Both: Have you participated in any MSCA ITN or DN projects? If yes, in how many and which projects?
2. MSCA: What motivated you to choose the MSCA programme for your research/idea over a national/regional funding or other scheme? Was it the budget offered by the MSCA grant, the EU dimension (which strongly supports more interdisciplinary/intersectoral/international collaboration opportunities) or anything else? Did you also apply with the same research proposal elsewhere?

Mobility (Intersectoral/International/Interdisciplinary):

3. Both: How do you initiate and establish collaborations with partners from different sectors, countries, and research disciplines? For MSCA: how has the funding helped you in developing these kinds of collaborations?
4. Both: According to you, what are the benefits and possible outcomes derived from international/intersectoral mobility and the interdisciplinary aspects of a project to the PhD students?

Training (Supervision/Working Environment):

5. Both (Explain MSCA training to non-MSCA supervisors): When comparing with non-MSCA schemes, what can PhD fellows get more from the training programmes funded by MSCA ITN/DN grant in terms of resources, training opportunities and acquisition of transversal skills? And what can they get more in training programmes funded by non-MSCA schemes that are missing in MSCA funding scheme?
- 6.1. MSCA: Did the ITN/DN programme influence your way of supervising doctoral candidates? If yes, how?
- 6.2. Non-MSCA: Did your knowledge about the ITN/DN programme influence your way of supervising doctoral candidates? If yes, how?

Structuring Effects:

7. Both: Have you seen an evolution in the doctoral programmes in the past 10 years (i.e., since 2014).
8. Both: If yes, what have been the main changes and their main triggers? How could the positive changes be further supported?
9. Both: Are you aware of successful approaches or best practices from ITN/DN projects that have been adopted by your institution/organisation? If yes, which ones?
10. Both: How has the ITN/DN funding contributed to the harmonization, and standardization of doctoral programmes in your institution?

Career Perspectives:

11. Both: Do you see any differences in the carrier perspectives between principal investigators who participate in ITN/DN funded projects and those who did not so far. If yes, which ones?

12. Both: Do you see any differences in the carrier perspectives between PhD students funded by an ITN/DN funded projects and the other PhD students. If yes, which ones?

Closing Question:

13. Both: Are there any complementary ideas that you would like to share with us about successful approaches or best practices from national/regional PhD programmes that should be implemented in the MSCA PhD programmes to improve their effectiveness and vice versa?

14.1. MSCA: Could you please explain to us what was the added value of having an MSCA ITN/DN grant and what aspects of it should be improved?

14.2. Non-MSCA: What aspects of the DN grant should be improved to motivate you or more organisations/research teams to apply for MSCA DN funding?

C. QUESTIONS FOR THE PROJECT MANAGERS

Opening Question:

1. How many and which MSCA ITN/DN projects have you managed? Have you managed other EU-funded grants? Have you managed national/regional doctoral programmes?

Mobility (Intersectoral/International/Interdisciplinary):

2. What are the biggest challenges of managing a network with entities from different countries, sectors, and research disciplines? How can these difficulties be overcome in general (or, in the context of ITN/DN, if applicable)?

3. What are the biggest challenges of managing the mobility aspects of the programme (e.g., secondments, visa, administrative support for incoming/outgoing fellows)? How can these difficulties be overcome in general (or, in the context of ITN/DN, if applicable)?

Training (Supervision/Working Environment):

4. How do you perceive the difference in managing an MSCA ITN/DN grant compared to a national/regional programme? What are the key advantages and/or challenges?

5. Have you participated in the proposal writing for ITN/DN? How easy was it to get information and apply? How can this be improved?

Structuring Effects:

6. How has the ITN/DN funding influenced the working conditions for researchers in your institution?

7. How has the implementation of MSCA ITN/DN programme impacted the internal organisation/collaboration between scientific departments and the administrative/support services?

Career Perspectives:

8. How did managing PhD projects influence your career perspectives? Do you think that the experience you gained from managing ITN/DN projects is an asset for your future career.

Closing Question:

9. What are the main differences between MSCA ITN/DN funding programme and other types of PhD funding? What are the main added values of the MSCA PhD programme and what are the best practices in project management from other PhD programmes that the MSCA PhD programmes could benefit from to improve their effectiveness?

D. QUESTIONS FOR OTHER STAKEHOLDERS

Opening Question:

1. How familiar are you with the MSCA PhD programme? Do you also have knowledge of national/regional PhD funding schemes?

Mobility (Intersectoral/International/Interdisciplinary):

2. In terms of mobility (international, intersectoral and interdisciplinary), do you believe there are differences between MSCA and nationally/regionally funded PhD programmes?

3. What are the biggest challenges/advantages to the PhD graduates, research teams and organisations in pursuing/facilitating/managing a project with international, intersectoral and interdisciplinary features?

Training (Supervision/Working Environment):

4. Is the MSCA ITN/DN programme attractive to the research community, specifically the bottom-up approach and the budget and access to platforms made available?

Structuring Effects:

5. Do you believe there is an added value to have three different implementation modes? What would make the ID/JD modes more attractive?

6. How has the MSCA programme influenced the research community (e.g., working conditions for researchers in an institution, fostering networking and collaborations) in your country, association, institution, etc.?

Career Perspectives:

7. In your opinion, how has the MSCA programme influenced the career perspectives of both the PhD students and the PIs participating in these projects?

Closing Questions:

8. What are the challenges and limitations to applying and implementing an MSCA ITN/DN project and how do you believe they could be addressed?

9. What are the main differences between MSCA ITN/DN funding programme and other types of PhD funding? What are the main added values of the MSCA PhD programme and what are the best practices in project management from other PhD programmes that the MSCA PhD programmes could benefit from to improve their effectiveness?

10. What suggestions do you have for attracting more organizations/research teams to participate in the MSCA DN calls? How do you support interested stakeholders to become aware of MSCA ITN/DN funding and create networks to apply for MSCA DN funding?